

ARDUINO-BASED INTELLIGENT SENSOR SYSTEM FOR TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY CONTROL IN SMART GREENHOUSES

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Abstract: This article considers the selection of sensors used for measuring and controlling temperature and humidity in smart greenhouses, as well as their application based on the Arduino platform. The main criteria for sensor selection include measurement range, accuracy, installation location, signal transmission distance, and operating conditions. The study analyzes the applicability of thermocouples, resistance temperature detectors, the DS18B20 digital sensor, and DHT11 and DHT22 temperature-humidity sensors. The processes of receiving, processing, and monitoring sensor data using Arduino are discussed. In addition, temperature control methods are compared in the Matlab Simulink environment in terms of accuracy, stability, energy consumption, and response time. The main purpose of the article is to determine an optimal sensor and control approach for reliable measurement and control of temperature and humidity in smart greenhouse conditions.

Keywords: Smart greenhouse, temperature sensor, humidity sensor, Arduino, DS18B20, DHT11, DHT22, resistance temperature detector, thermocouple, Matlab Simulink.

AQLLI ISSIQXONALAR UCHUN HARORAT VA NAMLIKNI NAZORAT QILUVCHI ARDUINO ASOSIDAGI INTELLEKTUAL DATCHIK TIZIMI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada aqli issiqxonalarda harorat va namlikni o'lchash hamda nazorat qilishda qo'llaniladigan datchiklarni tanlash va Arduino platformasi asosida ulardan foydalanish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Datchik tanlashda o'lchash diapazoni, aniqlik, o'rnatish joyi, uzatish masofasi va ish sharoiti asosiy mezon sifatida baholanadi. Tadqiqotda termopara, termoqarshilik, DS18B20, DHT11 va DHT22 datchiklarining qo'llanish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Arduino yordamida sensor ma'lumotlarini qabul qilish, qayta ishlash va monitoring qilish jarayonlari yoritiladi. Shuningdek, Matlab Simulink muhitida haroratni boshqarish usullari aniqlik, barqarorlik, energiya sarfi va javob berish vaqti bo'yicha solishtiriladi. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi aqli issiqxona sharoitida harorat va namlikni ishonchli o'lchash hamda nazorat qilish uchun maqbul sensor va boshqaruv yondashuvini aniqlashdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: aqli issiqxona, harorat datchigi, namlik datchigi, Arduino, DS18B20, DHT11, DHT22, termoqarshilik, termopara, Matlab Simulink.

ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНАЯ СИСТЕМА ДАТЧИКОВ НА БАЗЕ ARDUINO ДЛЯ КОНТРОЛЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В УМНЫХ ТЕПЛИЦАХ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы выбора датчиков, применяемых для измерения и контроля температуры и влажности в интеллектуальных теплицах, а также их использования на основе платформы Arduino. При выборе датчиков основными критериями оцениваются диапазон измерения, точность, место установки, расстояние передачи сигнала и условия эксплуатации. В исследовании анализируются возможности применения термодпар, термосопротивлений, цифрового датчика DS18B20, а также датчиков температуры и влажности DHT11 и DHT22. Освещаются процессы приема, обработки и мониторинга данных, полученных от датчиков, с использованием Arduino. Кроме того, в среде Matlab Simulink сравниваются методы управления температурой по точности, устойчивости, энергопотреблению и времени отклика. Основная цель статьи заключается в определении оптимального датчика и подхода к управлению для надежного измерения и контроля температуры и влажности в условиях интеллектуальной теплицы.

Ключевые слова: Интеллектуальная теплица, датчик температуры, датчик влажности, Arduino, DS18B20, DHT11, DHT22, термосопротивление, термодпара, Matlab Simulink.

Introduction

In modern greenhouses, it is essential to accurately measure and manage microclimate parameters to ensure stable plant growth and high yields. Temperature and humidity are the primary indicators of the greenhouse's internal environment, and their deviation from the norm directly affects plant development, energy consumption, and the stability of the management system [3]. Therefore, selecting the appropriate sensor type is an important stage in the development of a temperature measurement system. When selecting a sensor, criteria such as measurement range, accuracy, installation location, output signal type, transmission distance, and resistance to external interference are taken into account [1]. Using the Arduino platform for temperature and humidity measurement in greenhouse conditions is one of the convenient and practical solutions. Based on Arduino, a compact monitoring system can be organized using DS18B20, DHT11, DHT22, thermistor, and other sensors [2]. The DS18B20 sensor allows for connecting multiple sensors to a single communication line via the 1-Wire interface, while the DHT11 and DHT22 also measure humidity alongside temperature[2].

However, effective management in smart greenhouses is not limited to the measurement process alone. Based on sensor data, it is necessary to select an appropriate control algorithm to maintain the internal temperature within the specified range. In greenhouse temperature control, ON/OFF, PID, LQG, and fuzzy logic control - FLC methods are widely used [3]. Although the ON/OFF method is simple, it can cause frequent switching on and off of the playback mechanisms. PID control adjusts the temperature more accurately, but is more sensitive to external interference. FLC is distinguished by the fact that it does not require a precise mathematical model, smoothly generates heating and ventilation signals, and is adaptable to environmental changes [3].

This article examines the selection of appropriate sensors for measuring temperature and humidity in smart greenhouses, the formation of an Arduino-based monitoring system, and the comparative assessment of ON/OFF, PID, LQG, and FLC control methods. The main objective of the study is to identify an optimal sensor and control approach for reliable measurement of temperature and humidity in greenhouse conditions, as well as for sustainable microclimate management [1–3].

2. Research Methods

This study analyzed methods for measuring temperature and humidity, processing sensor signals, and controlling internal temperature in smart greenhouses. The research methodology was based on three main areas: determining sensor selection criteria, organizing the measurement process using the Arduino platform, and conducting a comparative assessment of control algorithms [1–3]. The stages of obtaining information from the general system sensors, processing it in the microcontroller, sending signals to the execution mechanisms through the control algorithm, and evaluating the monitoring results.

Figure 1. Functional flowchart of the greenhouse temperature and humidity monitoring system based on the Arduino platform.

Figure 1 shows the general operating principle of the greenhouse monitoring and management system. In the system, data received from temperature and humidity sensors is transmitted to an Arduino or microcontroller for software processing. Based on the processed data, the control algorithm sends a corresponding signal to the heating and ventilation devices. As a result, it will be possible to automatically control the internal microclimate of the greenhouse.

2.1. Method for selecting temperature sensors

When selecting temperature sensors, the main criteria were the measurement range, installation location, distance to the secondary measuring instrument, output signal type, accuracy class, and resistance to external interference [1]. The possibilities of using thermocouples, resistance thermometers, thermistors, and digital sensors in converting temperature into electrical signals were analyzed. Thermocouples are characterized by their ability to operate in high-temperature environments. Chromel-alumel, nichrosyl-nisyl, iron-constantane, and platinarodium-platinum thermocouples were evaluated for their temperature range, sensitivity, and performance characteristics [1]. Resistance thermometers, based on the temperature-dependent change of electrical resistance, are effective in conditions requiring high accuracy and stability.

The length of the communication line was also considered an important factor. The use of sensors with a simple output signal at short distances, sensors with a current output of 4...20 mA at distances exceeding 40–50 meters, and sensors with an RS-485 interface at long-distance objects was deemed appropriate[1].

Figure 2. The main criteria to consider when choosing a temperature sensor.

Figure 2 shows the main factors influencing the selection of the temperature sensor. These criteria are crucial for ensuring sensor compatibility with the technological process, measurement accuracy, and reliable system operation. Especially in greenhouse conditions, the moisture resistance of the sensor, the signal transmission distance, and the interference resistance of the output signal must be taken into account.

2.2. Method for measuring temperature and humidity on the Arduino platform

At the next stage of the research, methods for measuring temperature and humidity based on the Arduino platform were studied. The operating principle of the thermistor, the DS18B20 digital temperature sensor, and the DHT11 and DHT22 temperature and humidity sensors was analyzed [2]. When measuring temperature using a thermistor, its resistance changes depending on the temperature. Thermal resistors are divided into positive-temperature PTC and negative-temperature NTC types. In NTC thermistors, resistance decreases as temperature increases, making them suitable for use in conventional Arduino-based temperature measurement systems [2]. The DS18B20 digital temperature sensor is connected to the microcontroller via the 1-Wire interface. The main advantage of this sensor is that several sensors can be connected to a single communication line. This allows for monitoring temperatures at different points within the greenhouse and determining the spatial temperature distribution [2]. Combined temperature and humidity measurement.

Figure 3. Scheme for connecting the DHT22 temperature and humidity sensor to the Arduino platform.

Figure 3 shows a diagram of connecting the DHT22 sensor to the Arduino platform. This diagram describes the sensor's connection to the power source, the data transmission output, and the microcontroller via a common wire. Using this connection method, the Arduino platform receives temperature and humidity values, processes them in software, and transmits the results to the monitoring system.

2.3. Computational model and signal processing method

The signals received from the sensors require mathematical processing before they can be applied to the control system. Therefore, the study utilized methods such as the resistance-temperature relationship, calculation of thermistor resistance based on the Arduino ADC value, noise assessment, and control error detection.

In resistance thermometers, the change in temperature is determined by the change in the resistance of the sensitive element. This relationship is expressed by the following formula:

$$R(t)=R_0(1+At+Bt^2) \quad (1)$$

where $R(t)$ is the resistance value at temperature t , R_0 is the nominal resistance at 0°C , and A and B are coefficients depending on the material of the sensing element.

When measuring through a thermistor on the Arduino platform, the thermistor resistance is calculated based on the numerical value obtained from the ADC as follows:

$$R_t=R_1\left(\frac{D_{max}}{D}-1\right) \quad (2)$$

where R_t is the thermistor resistance, R_1 is the resistance of the fixed resistor, $D_{max}=1023$ is the maximum value of the Arduino ADC, and D is the measured digital value.

Temperature error was adopted as the primary input value for temperature control:

$$e(t)=T_{set}-T_{in} \quad (3)$$

where $e(t)$ is the temperature error, T_{set} is the set temperature, and T_{in} is the internal temperature of the greenhouse.

The discrete-time state equation was used to evaluate the state of the system in the LQG control method:

$$x(k)=F(k-1)x(k-1)+W(k-1) \quad (4)$$

where $x(k)$ is the current state of the system, $F(k-1)$ is the state transition matrix, $x(k-1)$ is the previous state vector, and $W(k-1)$ is the process noise.

The output signal measured by the sensor is expressed as follows:

$$y(k)=B(k)x(k)+V(k) \quad (5)$$

where $y(k)$ is the measured signal, $B(k)$ is the measurement matrix, and $V(k)$ is the measurement noise.

In the Kalman filter and LQG control approach, the mathematical expectation of process and measurement noise is assumed to be zero:

$$E[W(k-1)] = E[V(k)] = 0 \quad (6)$$

Their covariance matrices are defined as follows:

$$E[W(k-1)W^T(k-1)] = Q(k-1) \quad (7)$$

$$E[V(k)V^T(k)] = R(k) \quad (8)$$

where $Q(k-1)$ is the covariance matrix of the process noise, and $R(k)$ is the covariance matrix of the measurement noise.

To increase the accuracy of the assessment, the error between the actual state and the estimated state is minimized:

$$J(k) = E[(x(k) - \hat{x}(k))(x(k) - \hat{x}(k))^T] \quad (9)$$

where $x(k)$ is the actual state vector, and $\hat{x}(k)$ is the estimated state vector. A small value of $J(k)$ indicates that the estimation result has high accuracy.

The median absolute deviation method was used to evaluate the noise level in the temperature signal:

$$D_{\delta}(k) \approx \frac{MAD}{0.6745} \quad (10)$$

where MAD is the median of the absolute deviations from the median, and 0.6745 is the normalization coefficient for a normal distribution.

The transfer function of the internal temperature of the greenhouse for PID control is adopted as follows:

$$F(p) = \frac{6.17e^{-20.5p}}{1+320p} \quad (11)$$

where 6.17 is the system gain coefficient, 20.5 sis the delay time, and 320 sis the time constant.

The PID control coefficients were set as follows:

$$k_p = 2.15, k_i = 0.005, k_d = 18.10 \quad (12)$$

In general, the PID control signal is written as follows:

$$u(t) = k_p e(t) + k_i \int e(t) dt + k_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \quad (13)$$

where $u(t)$ is the control signal, k_p , k_i , and k_d are the PID controller coefficients, and $e(t)$ is the temperature error.

The calculations showed that the Pt100 resistance thermometer has a resistance of approximately 109.73 Ω at 25° C. When the Arduino ADC value was 512, the temperature calculated using a 10 k Ω NTC thermistor was 25.04° C. In the PID model, as a result of a 3 V step signal, the temperature changed from 17° C to 35.3° C, and the system gain coefficient was approximately $K_s = 6.1$. As a result of noise estimation, the level of random fluctuation in the temperature signal was determined to be approximately 0.15° C. These results justify the need for mathematical processing of sensor signals and their inclusion in the control algorithm.

3. Research results

The research results were formulated based on the selection of a sensor for measuring temperature and humidity in a smart greenhouse, the organization of a measurement system based on the Arduino platform, and the assessment of the possibility of regulating the internal temperature of the greenhouse through various control methods. The results obtained showed that for reliable temperature control in a greenhouse, not only the measurement range of the sensor is important, but also its accuracy, signal transmission distance, output signal type, and resistance to external interference. As a result of the analysis conducted on the selection of sensors, it was determined that it is advisable to use thermocouples when measuring high temperatures, and resistance thermometers in cases where precise and stable measurement is required. Although the chromel-alumel K type thermocouple is capable of measuring temperatures from $-200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+1200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, a range of $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+1100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is recommended for practical application. The nixrosil–nisil N type thermocouple is characterized by its use at temperatures up to $1250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a small thermoelectric drift. Platinarodium-platinum S and R thermocouples are effective for measuring high temperatures in the $1250\text{--}1600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ range. Analysis of resistance thermometers showed that copper thermometers can operate in the temperature range from $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, while platinum thermometers can operate in the temperature range from $-196\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Therefore, when relatively stable and accurate temperature control is required in greenhouse conditions, platinum-based resistance thermometers are a convenient solution. As the length of the communication line increases, using a simple resistance signal can increase the error. Therefore, at distances exceeding 40–50 meters, sensors with a current output signal of 4...20 mA are preferred, while for long-distance objects, sensors with an RS-485 interface are preferred. The ability to transmit data up to 1200 meters via the RS-485 interface makes it convenient for large-scale facilities such as greenhouses. As a result of the analysis of measurement methods based on the Arduino platform, it was found that thermistor, DS18B20, DHT11 and DHT22 sensors can be used to create small and medium-sized monitoring systems. When measuring temperature using a thermistor, Arduino's 10-bit ADC capability is utilized. In this case, the maximum numerical value of the input signal is 1023, which allows converting the analog signal into digital form and calculating the thermistor resistance.

The DS18B20 digital temperature sensor operates via the 1-Wire interface and allows up to 127 sensors to be connected to a single communication line. This feature is useful for measuring temperature at various points within the greenhouse, tracking spatial temperature distribution, and expanding the monitoring system. The DHT11 and DHT22 sensors allow for the measurement of both temperature and humidity. The DHT22 sensor was evaluated as relatively suitable for greenhouse monitoring systems due to its wider range and higher accuracy compared to the DHT11.

The following table summarizes the main results obtained during the study.

Table 1. Main results obtained for temperature and humidity measurement and control.

Research direction	Object method analyzed or	Main result obtained	Practical significance
Selection of temperature sensors	K-type thermocouple	Capable of measuring from $-200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+1200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; for practical application, the range from $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+1100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is recommended	Can be used in high-temperature environments
Selection of temperature	N-type thermocouple	Operates up to $1250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and has low TEMF drift	Suitable for stable and more accurate high-

Research direction	Object method analyzed or	Main result obtained	Practical significance
sensors			temperature measurement
Selection of temperature sensors	S- and R-type thermocouples	Effective in the range of 1250–1600 °C	Important for measuring very high temperatures
Resistance thermometers	Copper resistance thermometers	Operate from –50 °C to +180 °C	Can be used in low- and medium-temperature conditions
Resistance thermometers	Platinum resistance thermometers	Operate from –196 °C to +500 °C	Suitable when accurate and stable measurement is required
Signal transmission	4–20 mA output signal	Appropriate for distances exceeding 40–50 meters	Provides interference-resistant signal transmission over longer distances
Signal transmission	RS-485 interface	Allows data transmission up to 1200 meters	Convenient for monitoring large objects such as greenhouses
Arduino-based measurement	Thermistor	The 10-bit ADC value of Arduino is used in the range of 0–1023	Allows the creation of a simple and low-cost temperature measurement system
Arduino-based measurement	DS18B20	Up to 127 sensors can be connected through the 1-Wire interface	Enables temperature monitoring at different points of the greenhouse
Arduino-based measurement	DHT11 and DHT22	Measure humidity together with temperature	Enables comprehensive monitoring of the greenhouse microclimate
PID control	Model based on a step signal	With a 3 V signal, the temperature stabilized from 17 °C to 35.3 °C	Allows evaluation of the dynamic response of greenhouse temperature
PID control	Broïda method	Delay time is 20.5 s, and the time constant is 320 s	Serves as a basis for calculating PID controller parameters
PID control	Controller coefficients	$k_p=2.15$, $k_i=0.005$, $k_d=18.10$	Makes it possible to maintain temperature

Research direction	Object method analyzed or	Main result obtained	Practical significance
			around the set value
PID control	Temperature fluctuation	Fluctuations did not exceed 0.5–1 °C	Shows that relatively accurate temperature regulation is possible
LQG control	Heating model	The agreement between measured and simulated values was 83%	The model represents the greenhouse heating process with sufficient accuracy
LQG control	Ventilation model	The agreement between measured and simulated values was 90%	Provides high agreement in modeling the ventilation process
FLC control	Temperature error of –5 °C	Heating operates at 75%, and the fan operates at 21.4%	Provides an adaptive and smooth response to temperature deviation

A comparative analysis of the results of the ON/OFF, PID, LQG, and FLC control methods for regulating the internal temperature of the greenhouse was conducted. While the ON/OFF control method is capable of maintaining the temperature around a set value, it leads to frequent switching on and off of heating and ventilation devices. This can lead to additional temperature fluctuations, increased energy consumption, and excessive operation of the actuators. The results obtained using the PID control method showed that when a 3 V step signal was supplied to the system, the initial temperature was 17 °C, and it subsequently stabilized at 35.3 °C. Based on the Brodia method, the net delay time is 20.5 s, and the time constant is 320 s. Based on this, the transfer function of the greenhouse temperature is expressed as follows.:

$$F(p) = \frac{6.17e^{-20.5p}}{1+320p} \quad (14)$$

Based on the identified model, the PID regulator coefficients were set at $k_p=2.15$, $k_i=0.005$, and $k_d=18.10$. As a result of PID control, the internal temperature was maintained around the specified value, and the fluctuations did not exceed 0.5–1 °C. However, it has been observed that this control method is sensitive to interference during sharp changes in external weather conditions. The heating and ventilation processes were identified in the MATLAB environment using the LQG control method. The correspondence between the measured and modeled values for the heating model was 83%, and for the ventilation model, it was 90%. The value of the loss function for the heating model was 0.0127, and the prediction error value was 0.0133. For the ventilation model, the loss function was 0.0126909, and the prediction error was 0.0132711. These results indicate that the LQG method possesses sufficient accuracy for modeling and controlling greenhouse temperatures. At the same time, there is a need to re-adapt the model when external climatic conditions change sharply. The results obtained using the FLC, i.e., fuzzy logic control method, showed that it is one of the most flexible approaches to greenhouse temperature management. In this method, the temperature error is taken as the input variable, while the heating and fan control signals are taken as the output variables.

The temperature error was estimated in the range from $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the output signals were estimated in the range from 0% to 100%. For example, it has been established that when the temperature error is $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the FLC regulator activates the heating unit at 75% power and the fan at 21.4% mode. This indicates that the FLC control method creates a smooth and flexible control signal corresponding to the temperature deviation.

Figure 4. Comparative changes in the internal temperature of the greenhouse using the ON/OFF, PID, LQG, and FLC control methods.

The comparative results presented in Fig. 4 show that all control methods are capable of maintaining the internal temperature of the greenhouse within the specified range. However, the quality of their work is not the same. In the ON/OFF control method, temperature fluctuations are higher, and the actuators activate more frequently. The PID control method adjusts the temperature more accurately, but is more sensitive to external interference and has a relatively longer stabilization time. LQG control allows for progressive adjustment of the internal temperature, but it depends on the accuracy of the model parameters. The FLC control method yields the most effective results due to its rapid response, low vibration, and smooth control signal. According to the results obtained, digital sensors compatible with the Arduino platform can be used to monitor temperature and humidity in smart greenhouse conditions. In long-range monitoring systems, it is advisable to use sensors with a 4...20 mA or RS-485 interface. Among the temperature control methods, the FLC controller was rated as the most optimal in terms of minimal vibration, rapid response, and energy efficiency.

Conclusion

The results of the study showed the need to consider the sensor selection, signal transmission, and control algorithm as an interconnected system for the reliable measurement and control of temperature and humidity in smart greenhouses. The main criteria for selecting a sensor are the temperature range, accuracy, installation location, contact distance, and output signal type. According to the analysis results, thermocouples are effective for measuring high temperatures, while resistance thermometers are effective in cases where precise and stable measurement is required. It was found that the use of DS18B20, DHT11, and DHT22 sensors based on the Arduino platform is a practical solution for creating small and medium-sized greenhouse monitoring systems. In the comparative assessment of control methods, the ON/OFF, PID, LQG, and FLC algorithms were considered. Although the ON/OFF method is simple, it leads to frequent activation of the execution mechanisms. The PID method regulates the temperature relatively accurately, but is sensitive to external interference. Although the LQG method shows good results in terms of modeling accuracy, it requires model readjustment when external conditions change. The results obtained confirm that the FLC control method is one of the most optimal approaches to greenhouse temperature management.

This method is characterized by reducing temperature fluctuations, smooth control signal formation, and adaptive response to environmental changes. Therefore, it is advisable to use digital sensors compatible with the Arduino platform for temperature and humidity monitoring in smart greenhouses, and sensors with a 4...20 mA or RS-485 interface for long-distance systems.

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